

The first Trans-continental Networking Academy for
African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.

D1.4 Data Management Plan – Year 1

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Glossary and Abbreviations

DM	Dissemination Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
PC	Project Coordinator
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	6
1. Data Summary.....	6
1.1 Data from AfriConEU	6
1.2 Data from External Sources	8
2. FAIR Data.....	8
2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	8
2.2 Making data openly accessible.....	9
2.3 Making data interoperable	9
2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	9
3. Allocation of resources	9
4. Data security	10
5. Ethical issues	10
5.1 General Data Protection Regulation	11
5.2 Sensitive Data	11

List of Tables

Table 1 - Data Type Generated by AfriConEU.....	6
Table 2 - Data Description and Purposes.....	7
Table 3 – Members of the Ethics Board.....	9

Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is intended to support partners in the secure and effective use and management of the research data collected and generated within the AfriConEU project. It presents the types of research data that will be generated or collected during the project, the standards that will be used, how the research data will be preserved and what parts of the datasets will be shared for verification or reuse. Importantly, AfriconEU empirical research will generate data from the quantitative surveys, interviews to relevant stakeholders, focus groups, roundtables and workshops. The qualitative research data will not be made openly accessible as primary data but in a processed form as reports.

This DMP will be revised and updated by Month 18 and by Month 30 to reflect the evolving activities and needs of the project implementation, as well as to achieve a sound data management throughout. In particular, the updated versions of the DMP will provide details on particular issues such as data interoperability and improved data management procedures.

1. Data Summary

1.1 Data from AfriConEU

The AfriConEU foresees several activities of data collection which is essential to achieve the project objectives. Table 1 presents the data type, the activity originating the data, the associate WP in which the activity takes place and the format in which the data will be likely stored.

Table 1 - Data Type Generated by AfriConEU

Data Type	WP	Activity originating the data	Storage format
Stakeholder contacts list	2 6	Publicly available data Primary data	.xls + .docx
Interview data collection	2	Primary data	.docx + .txt
Roundtable data collection	2	Primary data	.mp3 + .docx + .txt
Online survey data	2	Primary data	.xls + .csv
Focus group data collection	2	Primary data	.mp3 + .docx + .txt
Design Thinking Bootcamps data	3	Primary data	.docx + .txt

Table 2 describes the data type and the purpose of the data collection within the scope of the project.

Table 2 - Data Description and Purposes

Data Type	Description	Purpose
Stakeholder contacts list	The data contain information on the project stakeholders (e.g., representatives of Digital Innovation Hubs, Tech Hubs, Business Incubator Networks, Co-working Spaces, Accelerators, Local entrepreneurial and Startup community supporters, Entrepreneurs, etc). The contact information that is collected includes the name, institutional affiliation, position, email address and office location.	The collection will be used for contacting the project stakeholders to engage on the empirical research activities. It also provides the basis for the dissemination actions planned in the project.
Interview data collection	The data consists of written notes from about 15 interviews with DIHs and other stakeholders and about 20 trainers/facilitators/participants and 100 trainees. The interviews will be conducted via telephone and/or via VoIP services (e.g. Skype).	The collection will be used to identify existing challenges and needs for strengthening local DIHs, as well as exploring existing initiatives and programmes focused on enforcing DIHs. Findings will influence the development of the AfriConEU Networking Academy programmes.
Roundtable data collection	The data consists of written notes and summaries from 4 roundtable discussions to be held in Akure, Kampala, Kumasi and Dar es Salaam with a total of 40 representatives from startups, SMEs, DIHs, government, investor networks etc.	The collection will be used to provide insights about the maturity level and the needs of the local ecosystems to influence the development of the AfriConEU Networking Academy programmes.
Online survey data	The data contains answers from at least 200 stakeholders, including African entrepreneurs. The survey will be run as an online questionnaire.	The collection will be used to identify existing challenges and needs for strengthening local DIHs, including at the level of capacity building. It will influence the development of the Capacity Building Flagship Programme.
Focus group data collection	The data consists of protocols, recordings, notes and summaries from 3 online focus groups bringing together representatives from DIHs from Europe and Africa.	The collection will be used to identify current perceptions towards cross-continental and intracontinental partnerships and define needs and preferences. It will influence the development of the Trans-Continental Partnership Development Flagship Programme.
Design Thinking Bootcamps data	The data contain protocols, written notes and summaries done at the 4 design thinking bootcamps to be organised in each one of the targeted African countries, and addressing digital ecosystem stakeholders and experts from Europe and Africa.	The collection will be used to support the ideation for joint programme development between EU-AU actors.

1.2 Data from External Sources

The AfriConEU project entails activities that will require accessing to secondary data, namely EU-wide available on a variety of sources, including EUROSTAT. In fact, partners will review the literature (studies, blog postings, white papers, consultancy reports etc.) focusing on Africa's tech hubs, and about existing initiatives and programmes focused on strengthening DIHs capacities both in Africa and in Europe. This collection will be essential to develop the *D2.2 Online data base with DIHs Capacity Building programmes* and the *D3.4 Inventory of capacity building resources and ready to use training material*, which are meant to be made available online in a searchable format to facilitate reuse.

2. FAIR Data

Following the guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020¹, the next sub-sections present the main considerations of AfriConEU partners to ensure proper sharing and management of the data collected.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data and project results will be shared with the relevant communities through publications as well as through open access data repositories. An important aspect for making data findable is to attribute a suitable naming convention to project data.

In this sense, datasets generated during the project will use a name convention as follows: **AfriConEU_WPxx_TXx_DDMMYYYY_.doc**, i.e. acronym of the project + WP generating the dataset + Task generating the dataset + data of creation with format DDMMYYYY + dataset format. As for project reports/deliverables, name segments should be as follows: **AfriConEU_D1.1_15032021_V01.doc** – meaning that the report consist on Version 1 of the Deliverable D1.1 produced on 15 March 2021.

The AfriConEU metadata will be in a standard format and will include all the following: i) the terms "European Union (EU)" and "Horizon 2020"; ii) the name of the action, acronym and grant number; iii) the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and iv) a persistent identifier.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

2.2 Making data openly accessible

AfriConEU participates in the Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020 and will therefore offer open access to data generated, as well as to relevant publications and reports produced throughout the project lifetime.

In addition to the project SharePoint, which is password-protected and only accessible by partners, relevant datasets will be also stored in ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org>) - the open access repository of OpenAIRE, the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (<https://www.openaire.eu>).

2.3 Making data interoperable

The data produced and/or used in the project should be interoperable allowing data exchange between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. Interoperability will be supported by using standard metadata and file formats. To be further detailed in DMP – Year 2 (D1.5 - Month 18).

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Public data will be made available for re-use. Data will be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible when no limitations are identified by the key stakeholders. To be further detailed in DMP – Year 2 (D1.5 - Month 18).

3. Allocation of resources

In compliance with the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC and with Article 29 Working Party 8/2010 opinion, a Data Controller is appointed as part of WP1 – Pedro Castro (INOVA+), responsible to the project coordinator and having the appropriate local registration; other partners will act as Data Processors in connection with their specific responsibilities and tasks.

The consortium includes an Ethics Board made up of the coordinator and one member from each partner (Table 3). All issues pertaining to ethics approval will be forwarded to the Ethics Board for notification and approval.

Table 3 – Members of the Ethics Board

Partner	Representative of the Partner	Partner	Representative of the Partner
INOVA+	Miguel Sousa	STMLI	Irene Kalemaki
ECA	Peace Odili	ITC	Sasa Straus
YMH	Marilena Maragkou	BUNI	Edwin Bakalemwa

Partner	Representative of the Partner	Partner	Representative of the Partner
PBS	Catarina Reis	ATBN	Eunice Ball
OUTBOX	Richard Zulu	HAPA	Douglas Boateng
DPIXEL	Stefano Azzalin		

By concerning the whole project, data management will be of the responsibility of partners according to their specific responsibilities and tasks, but particularly of the Project Coordinator (as Data Controller), the Work Package Leaders who are responsible to ensure the implementation of the data management procedures in their respective WP, and of the Dissemination Manager who shall monitor that publications produced by the project are clearly identified and assist and advice partners on diffusion paths.

The costs related to the data management activities will be detailed in DMP – Year 2 (D1.5 - Month 18).

4. Data security

To ensure the security of the data, the following procedures shall be followed by members of the AfriConEU consortium:

- ✓ Store data in at least two separate locations to avoid loss of data;
- ✓ Perform regular and appropriate backups to avoid loss of data;
- ✓ Encrypt data if it is deemed necessary by the participating researchers;
- ✓ Label files in a systematically structured way in order to ensure the coherence of the final dataset (as described in 2.1).
- ✓ Limit the use of USB flash drives.

Data is to be stored in the project SharePoint on MStTeams which is password-protected and only accessible by partners. Data stored on SharePoint will be kept for 5 years after the end of the project and made available for third parties upon request. Data shared through ZENODO will be available according to the repository access rules.

5. Ethical issues

AfriConEU project and all those involved from beneficiary and partner organisations will conduct research and commit to abide strictly to the principles of:

- ✓ Respecting human dignity and integrity;
- ✓ Ensuring honesty and transparency towards participants and notably getting free and informed consent;

- ✓ Protecting vulnerable persons;
- ✓ Ensuring privacy and confidentiality;
- ✓ Sharing the benefits with disadvantaged populations;
- ✓ Following the highest standards of research integrity (i.e. avoiding any kind of fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, unjustified double funding, or other type of research misconduct) as defined in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

5.1 General Data Protection Regulation

AfriConEu will comply with the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon 2020 regulations that apply to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and in accordance with the international and EU Directives/Regulations, as well as respective national iterative.

The AfriConEu Online Community will be designed to facilitate interactions between the project community and its different stakeholders around DIHs and start-ups. Users will be able to interact with like-minded users to exchange knowledge, experiences, contacts, increase their visibility and be supported. They will self-certify during registration that they are adults (18-65) and they will agree with the legal terms and regulations.

5.2 Sensitive Data

Collection of personal data may take place during the various initiatives of the project; the surveys focus groups, interviews, workshops, and the different events. Participants will be given information about how their data will be collected, protected during the project and either destroyed or re-used at the end of the project. In the latter case, they will be reminded that they may withhold such data; and that any such additional activities will remain strictly within the bounds covered by their informed consent form.

Non-professional personal data, if collected, will be stored securely on a password-protected computer, only used for the purpose for which it was collected. If a plan to reuse data is considered, participants will be given information about this as soon as it becomes available and be given the opportunity to consent or withdraw their data.

Further insights will be provided in DMP – Year 2 that will provide details of the initial data collection as well as of the informed consent procedures.